

Synthesis and Plant Growth Retardant Activity of Trialkylammonium Iodide from Acyclic Compounds

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Quaternary salts of ammonia derived from terpenoids and straight chain compounds¹ have shown plant growth retarding effects. In continuation of our work on the synthesis and biological studies of quaternary ammonium halides, we have undertaken the synthesis and plant growth retarding activity of eight new quaternary salts of ammonia derived from citronellol and decanol, which have been here.

reacted with diethylamine and K_2CO_3 in acetone³ to get *N,N*-diethyl-2-(3',7'-dimethyl-6'-octenoxy)-aminoethane (2). Dichloromethylene was introduced at the double bond of the tertiary amine (2) by refluxing 2 with catalytic amount of benzyltriethylammonium chloride and aqueous NaOH in chloroform⁴.

The *n*-bromodecane (8) obtained by the bromination of decanol with PBr_3 in dry ether in the presence of pyridine was converted into *N,N*-diethylaminodecane (9) by refluxing it with diethylamine and K_2CO_3 in dry acetone³. *N,N*-Dimethylaminodecane was prepared by heating decanal (12) and DMF and $HCOOH$ ⁵. The tertiary amines 2, 5, 9 and 10 were then quaternised by treating with methyl and ethyl iodides in dry ether.

The quaternary salts (3, 4, 6, 7, 10, 11, 14 and 15) were tested for their biological activity as growth retardants on turnip seeds (*Brassica rapa*, Var. 4-Red). Three replications of each experiment were kept in the manner reported in literature⁶. The data obtained has been statistically analysed by applying complex RBD function and the value of CD at 5% level for compounds, and concentration are given in Table 1. Compound 7 with dichloropropyl ring and 14, showed strong inhibitory effect at higher concentration (100 ppm).

Citronellol on treatment with ethylenebromide in the presence of NaH in $DMSO^2$ produced 2-(3',7'-dimethyl-6'-octenoxy)bromoethane (1) in quantitative yield. The crude bromide (1) was

Experimental

Boiling and melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) were taken on a EM 360/390

TABLE I—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF COMPOUNDS ON TURNIP SEEDS SEED GERMINATION, AFTER 72 h

Compd no.	Percentage germination				Seedling length (cm)			
	10	25	50	100	10	25	50	100
3	96	96	94	88	4.187	3.987	3.147	2.088
4	100	100	88	88	4.160	3.766	2.096	2.822
6	94	92	90	88	4.695	4.213	4.210	4.062
7	94	94	76	46	4.389	3.057	1.995	0.456
10	100	98	96	84	4.628	3.863	3.085	2.738
11	98	92	92	88	4.775	4.219	3.617	3.562
14	88	88	80	32	4.643	3.775	3.108	0.625
15	94	94	90	52	4.391	4.344	3.316	2.817
CD at 5% (compound) A		1.52				0.0152		
CD at 5% (concentration) B		1.08				0.0107		
CD at 5% (compound × concentration) A × B		3.04				0.030		
Control			% germination				Seedlings length (average)	
ABA (5 mg/l)			4				0.850	
Water			100				4.480	

spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer.

2-(3',7'-Dimethyl-6'-octenoxy)bromoethane (1) : To the stirred suspension of NaH (13.80 g; 50%) in DMSO (60 ml), a solution of citronellol (20 g) in DMSO (14 ml) was added at room temperature. After stirring for 1 h, dibromoethane (25 g) was added slowly and stirring continued for 15 h. It was then poured into cold water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was washed with water and aqueous sodium thiosulphate successively and dried. The residue obtained after distillation of the solvent was chromatographed over silica gel, using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) as eluent to give the product (20.30 g, 50%).

N,N-Diethyl-2-(3',7'-dimethyl-6'-octenoxy)aminoethane (2) : A mixture of the bromide (1; 20 g), diethylamine (6.7 g) and K₂CO₃ (10 g) was stirred with acetone (100 ml) at 60° for 6 h. Reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was distilled. Water (50 ml) was then added, the solution was extracted with ether and the ether extract dried over Na₂SO₄. The residue obtained after removal of ether was vacuum-distilled to give the product (10 g, 52%), b.p. 105–07°/6–8 mm (Found : C, 75.37; H, 12.87; N, 5.49. C₁₆H₃₃ON requires : C, 75.29; H, 12.94; N, 5.49%); v_{\max} 3 100w, 2 980, 2 945, 2 890, 1 660,

1 465, 1 390, 1 345, 1 120, 1 065, 1 040, 900 and 835 cm⁻¹; δ 0.90–0.96 (9H, bs, sat. CH₃), 1.34 (4H, m, saturated CH₂), 1.60, 1.63 (3H each, s, vinylic CH₃), 1.90 (2H, m, allylic CH₂), 2.40–2.78 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂), 3.55 (4H, m, CH₂OCH₂) and 5.1 (1H, s, vinylic H).

N,N-Diethyl-2-(6',7'-dichloromethylene-3',7'-dimethyl-octanoxy)aminoethane (5) : To a vigorously stirred mixture of the tertiary amine (2; 2 g), chloroform (2.4 ml) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (30 mg), a solution of NaOH (1.8 g in 2 ml of water) was added slowly in 5 min. Within 2 min, an emulsion was formed and the temperature of the mixture was increased slowly during 25 min to a maximum 50–60°. The temperature was then decreased when the colour changed. Chloroform layer was then separated and aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined ether extract was washed with 2M HCl followed by water. It was then dried, the solvent removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to get the product (75%, 1.9 g), b.p. 108–10°/8–10 mm (Found : C, 58.81; H, 10.19; N, 4.35. C₁₆H₃₃ONCl₂ requires : C, 58.89; H, 10.12; N, 4.29%); v_{\max} 2 970, 2 945, 2 880, 1 455, 1 380, 1 265, 1 030, 820 and 805 cm⁻¹; δ 0.4 (1H, bs, cyclopropane-H), 0.9 (3H, sat. CH₃), 1.0–1.2 (18H, m, -N(CH₂CH₃)₂, (CH₃)₂C-CCl₂, saturated methylene), 2.40–2.50 (6H, -CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂) and 3.3–3.5 (4H, m, CH₂OCH₂).

N,N-Diethylaminodecane (**9**) : A mixture of bromodecane (**8**; 2 g), diethylamine (0.8 g) and K_2CO_3 (1 g) was stirred with acetone at 60° for 6h. The reaction mixture was then filtered and most of the acetone was removed by distillation. It was diluted with water (15 ml) and extracted with ether. The combined extract was dried and the residue after removal of the solvent was vacuum-distilled to get the product (52%, 1 g), b.p. $92-94^\circ/6-7$ mm (Found : C, 85.54; H, 14.42; N, 6.48. $C_{14}H_{33}N$ requires : C, 85.44; H, 14.55; N, 6.57%); ν_{max} 2 980, 2 950, 2 080, 1 475, 1 385, 1 300, 1 250, 1 070, 1 000 and 750 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.9 (3H, sat. CH_3) and 1.1 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $N(CH_2CH_3)_2$).

N,N-Dimethylaminodecane (**13**) : A mixture of decanal (**12**; 2.5 g), DMF (3.5 g) and formic acid (85%; 2 g) was heated at 190° for 6 h. The resulting cold dark yellow homogenous solution was acidified with 10% HCl (30 ml) and extracted with ether to remove any unreacted aldehyde. The acidic solution was then made alkaline with 10% NaOH and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by vacuum-distillation of the residue afforded the product (87%, 2.6 g), b.p. $101-103^\circ/7-9$ mm (Found : C, 77.76; H, 14.70; N, 7.47. $C_{12}H_{27}N$ requires : C, 77.83; H, 14.59; N, 7.56%); ν_{max} 2 980, 2 870, 1 460, 1 390 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.9 (3H, t, J 3 Hz, sat. CH_3), 1.3 (16H, bs, sat. CH_2), 2.66 (6H, s, $N(CH_3)_2$) and 2.9 (2H, t, J 3 Hz $CH_2N(CH_3)_2$).

Quaternary salts. General procedure : To a cold (5°) solution of **13** (500 mg) in dry ether (15 ml), methyl iodide (1 ml) was added slowly and the mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. It was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight and the hygrscopic precipitate obtained by centrifugation was stored in dry ether (yield 0.4 g, 45%). All other quaternary salts of ammonia were prepared similarly by treating the different tertiary amines (**2**, **5** and **9**) with methyl and ethyl iodides.

Plant growth retardant activities : 25 seeds of turnip (*Brassica raps*, Var. 4-Red) in three replications were placed on a filter paper laid on the bottom of a petri dish of 9 cm diameter containing 10 ml of test solution of different concentrations of the compounds. Each dish was kept at $25 \pm 2^\circ$ for 72 h and then the percent seed germination and seedling lengths were recorded.

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